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Title: In Vitro Insect Muscle for Tissue Engineering Applications

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Abstract

Tissue engineering is primarily associated with medical disciplines, and research has thus focused on mammalian cells. For applications where clinical relevance is not a constraint, it is useful to evaluate the potential of alternative cell sources to form tissues in vitro. Specifically, skeletal muscle tissue engineering for bioactuation and cultured foods could benefit from the incorporation of invertebrate cells, due to their less stringent growth requirements and other versatile features. Here, we used a *Drosophila* muscle cell line to demonstrate the benefits of insect cells relative to those derived from vertebrates. The cells were adapted to serum-free media, transitioned between adherent and suspension cultures, and manipulated with hormones. Furthermore, we analyzed scaffolds to support cell adhesion and assayed cellular protein and minerals to evaluate nutrition potential. The insect muscle cells exhibited advantageous growth patterns and hold unique functionality for tissue engineering applications beyond the medical realm.

Key Words: insect cell culture, skeletal muscle tissue engineering, chitosan scaffolds, bioactuation, cellular agriculture, cultured meat

Introduction

Advances in tissue engineering have driven the emergence of new products and industries beyond the realm of regenerative medicine, including organs-on-a-chip, soft robotics and biofabricated food and materials. Specifically, skeletal muscle tissue engineering is now being applied for the development of muscle-powered bio-bots and bioengineered meat, also known as cultured meat^{1,2}. These applications are not constrained by concerns of immunogenicity, host-integration or *in vivo*-like function. Instead, relevant challenges include lowering costs and achieving efficient, large-scale production so that tissue engineered commodities can be competitive against their conventional counterparts (e.g., electrical actuators and agriculturally farmed meat)³. Muscle tissue produced as food should also be visually and texturally similar to farmed meat, appealing to consumers and nutritionally advantageous⁴. Conversely, bioactuators should generate large contractile force, operate under a range of environmental conditions and incorporate control systems⁵. Insect cells are potentially better suited than mammalian cells to address many of these objectives.

Commonly used cells for skeletal muscle tissue research include the mouse myoblast cell line C2C12, the rat myoblast cell line L6, and human cells obtained from primary lines or induced pluripotent stem cells⁶. These cell types are typically grown as adherent cultures at 37°C with 5% carbon dioxide in sodium bicarbonate-buffered basal medium supplemented with fetal bovine serum. These conditions, while feasible for bench-scale culture, create hurdles for

achieving cost-efficient production at scale for commercial cell-based products. Specifically, animal serum is costly and inconsistent, above ambient incubation temperatures require increased energy use, and adherent cell lines need complex substrates (e.g., microcarriers, hollow fibers) for high density growth in bioreactor systems^{7,8}.

In contrast, many insect cell lines are able to transition between adherent and suspension culture, and are best suited for temperatures within the ambient range of 19-30°C and slightly acidic pH levels (6.2-6.4)⁹⁻¹¹. Unlike vertebrate cells, insect cells can be grown in a non-humidified environment and do not require CO₂ exchange¹². It is also reported to be relatively simple to adapt insect cells to both serum-free medium and suspension culture¹³. Furthermore, immortal or continuous insect cell lines are straightforward to obtain compared to vertebrate species, and many lines have been observed to retain their phenotype after over 120 cell doublings^{10,11}. In our prior study of *Manduca sexta*, primary cells maintained viability in culture for a month without media refreshment¹⁴. This set of unique culture characteristics make insect cells a particularly promising platform for novel applications of tissue engineering, and could contribute to scalable, cost-effective production systems for bioactuators and food.

Bioactuators are theorized to be advantageous over conventional actuators due to their efficiency and sustainability, and their capacity for self-assembly, self-healing and biodegradation¹⁵. The majority of bioactuator research at cellular and tissue levels has focused on mammalian cardiac or skeletal cells or insect dorsal vessel explants⁵. The general research strategy is to couple cultured cells or tissues with scaffold systems to perform mechanical work. For example, cardiomyocyte cell sheets have been combined with polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) constructs to create a micropump with linear flow rates of 2 nL/mL¹⁶. PDMS molds

have similarly been used with skeletal muscle cells to create microtissues under optogenetic control¹⁷. Insect tissue explants have also been of interest due to their tolerance of temperature fluctuations. Explanted DVT has been attached to PDMS molded devices which were operable at room temperature and generated 20 μ N force¹⁸. In our own studies, we used cells isolated from embryos of the tobacco hawkmoth (*Manduca sexta*) to make simple muscle fiber bioactuators that contracted under a wide range of temperature, pH and nutrient conditions¹².

Cultured meat is another innovation derived from advances in muscle tissue engineering. By producing meat from cell cultures rather than whole organisms (e.g., farm animals), it is emerging as a potential solution to global food issues. Cultured muscle tissue production generally consists of (1) obtaining cells from an immortalized line or biopsy isolation, (2) proliferating the cells at scale in a serum-free media, and (3) differentiating the cells into muscle on an edible, degradable or reusable scaffold². Research in this field has gained traction since 2013, when a cultured beef burger “proof of concept” was produced⁴. Skeletal muscle development from porcine induced pluripotent stem cells has since been reported, offering a potentially reliable farm animal-derived cell line for food technology¹⁹. Primary muscle cell lines from chicken, cow, pig and horse have also been isolated and differentiated *in vitro*²⁰. Additional progress has been made on the development of sustainable and edible scaffold systems. Cellulose-based scaffolds fabricated from decellularized plants (e.g., spinach, apples) have been shown to support mammalian muscle growth^{21,22}.

Reliable cell sources, serum-free media formulations and 3D scaffold systems must be developed in order for insect muscle tissue engineering to be applied for bioactuator and cultured meat development. To date, *in vitro* insect muscle research has utilized explants or

primary cells isolated from insect tissue. However, primary cell isolates result in mixed cell cultures and require frequent and labor-intensive isolation procedures¹⁴. A *Drosophila melanogaster* adult muscle immortalized progenitor-like cell line may be a promising initial cell source for insect tissue engineering because the cells (1) express GFP for ease of imaging, (2) are highly proliferative, (3) can differentiate upon treatment with the insect molting hormone 20-hydroxyecdysone¹⁰. It is important for the culture medium to be serum-free, low-cost and support muscle growth and differentiation. Fortunately, there are many commercial and “homemade” serum-free media formulations available for insect cells which can be verified or adapted to support muscle-specific cells²³. There is also a need for the design of affordable scaffold systems capable of supporting 3D insect muscle constructs. Mushroom-derived chitosan is a promising biomaterial for development of such scaffolds, as it is easily accessible, edible, widely used in tissue engineering and already incorporated in food products as an additive or dietary supplement²⁴. The combination of stable insect muscle cell lines, optimized media and scaffolding techniques will allow for further evaluation and analysis of the potential applications of insect muscle tissue engineering.

The objective of the present work was to evaluate the potential of *D. melanogaster* muscle cells to serve as a platform for tissue engineering applications. To accomplish this goal, we assessed moderate-scale production (e.g., serum-free culture, suspension culture, hormone regulation schemes), analyzed 3D culture systems via mushroom-derived chitosan scaffolding and quantified cellular levels of protein and minerals for nutritional insight.

Experimental Section

Materials & Methods

Cell Culture - *Drosophila melanogaster* adult muscle progenitor-like cells (DrAMPCs) were acquired from Kerafast (Boston, MA) (#EF4006). The cell line was originally immortalized by the Persimmon Research Group at Harvard University, and was derived from primary embryo cultures in which Gal4 drives Ras^{V12} and GFP expression. DrAMPCs were cultured in insect growth media composed of Schneider's Insect Medium from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO) (#S0146) supplemented with 10% heat inactivated fetal bovine serum from ThermoFisher (Waltham, MA) (#16140) and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (ThermoFisher, #15140122). For serum-free growth media experiments, media consisted of Ex-Cell 405 Serum-Free Medium (Sigma-Aldrich, #14405C) and 1% penicillin/streptomycin. For static culture, DrAMPCs were cultured in either plasma-treated flasks (ThermoFisher, #156499) or ultra-low attachment flasks (Corning, NY) (#CLS3814) and incubated at 19°C in a temperature-controlled incubator from VWR (Radnor, PA) (#89511-416). For suspension culture, DrAMPCs were cultured in shaker flasks (ThermoFisher, #4115-0250) on an orbital shaker set at 40 rpm at room temperature. When indicated, dextran sulfate (Sigma-Aldrich, #67578) was supplemented to serum-free media by dissolution and sterile filtration with 0.2 µm bottle top filters (ThermoFisher, #595-3320). For hormone treatment and differentiation experiments, DrAMPCs were cultured in insect growth media or serum-free media supplemented with methoprene (Sigma-Aldrich, #33375) and/or 20-hydroxyecdysone (Sigma-Aldrich, #H5142) which were dissolved in DMSO (Sigma-Aldrich, #D8418). DrAMPCs were seeded at 75,000 or 300,000 cells/cm² in 2D culture and 1,000,000 cells/sponge in 3D culture. For mammalian controls, C2C12 cells from ATTC (Manassas, VA) (#CRL-1772) were cultured in growth media composed of DMEM + Glutamax (ThermoFisher, #10566) supplemented with 10% heat

inactivated fetal bovine serum and 1% penicillin/streptomycin. C2C12s were seeded at 10,000 cells/cm².

Adhesion, Proliferation and Viability Assays - Cell adhesion to tissue culture plastic and chitosan films was quantified via a MTS Assay from Promega (Madison, WI) (#G3582) by measuring absorbance after 2.5-hour incubation with the MTS reagent. Cell proliferation and viability were measured by fluorescence, Live/Dead kit (ThermoFisher, #L3224) stained image analysis or CyQuant proliferation assays (ThermoFisher, #C7026). For fluorescence measurements, GFP-expressing DrAMPCs were imaged on a fluorescence microscope over the course of a week using the automated multi-point capture feature. Fluorescence was quantified on Fiji software and normalized to the values determined at the first time-point. For Live/Dead stained image analysis, cells were stained following the kit protocols and imaged on a fluorescence microscope. The images were analyzed with Fiji to quantify the viability and total cell population over time. For CyQuant proliferation assays, cells were plated in 96-well plates for each time-point. At each time-point, media was blotted from the plates and plates were stored at -80°C. After all time-points were collected, plates were thawed to room temperature and stained with CyQuant working solution for 5 minutes. Microplate measurements were performed on a SpectraMax M2 reader from Molecular Devices (San Jose, CA). Cell populations were determined from a standard curve.

Staining and Imaging - Cell viability was determined by a Live/Dead staining kit (ThermoFisher, #L3224). At time of assay, media was gently aspirated from the cell surface and cells were rinsed with phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (ThermoFisher, #14040133). Cells were stained with 2 µM calcein AM and 4 µM EthD-1 solution for 30 minutes at room temperature in the dark

and imaged with a fluorescence microscope. For immunocytochemical staining, media was gently aspirated from cells and the cell surface was rinsed with PBS. Cells were fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde from Fisher Scientific (Hampton, NH) (#J61899AK) for 10 minutes and rinsed with PBS. Cells were then permeabilized with 0.5% Triton X-100 and rinsed with blocking buffer consisting of phosphate buffered saline, 5% fetal bovine serum and 0.05% sodium azide. Cells were incubated in blocking buffer for 15 minutes before addition of primary antibody, then incubated at 4°C overnight. Cells were rinsed and incubated with fresh blocking buffer for 15 minutes before addition of secondary antibody, then incubated in the dark on ice for 1 hour. Again, cells were rinsed and incubated with fresh blocking buffer for 15 minutes before counterstaining and mounting with DAPI mounting medium from Abcam (Cambridge, UK) (#ab104139). Detailed antibody information is available in Table SI2. Fluorescence imaging was performed on a Keyence microscope (Osaka, Japan) (#BZ-X700). Confocal imaging was performed on a TCS SP8 microscope from Leica Microsystems (Wetzlar, Germany).

Scaffold Fabrication - Mushroom chitosan of 100 kDa molecular weight from Chinova Bioworks (New Brunswick, Canada) was dissolved in 2% acetic acid in distilled water for 12 hours at room temperature on a stir plate. The chitosan solution was centrifuged at 16,880 xg for 3 hours to remove undissolved particles and diluted in distilled water to the desired concentrations (1%, 2% and 4%). Concentrations were verified by drying small volumes at 60°C for 2 hours and calculating dry weight/wet weight. To prepare films, the solution was cast on plastic and allowed to dry overnight. To prepare sponges, the solution was poured into PDMS molds with an aluminum sheet separating one side of the mold from a separate chamber. Liquid nitrogen was poured into the chamber opposite the chitosan solution and

continually replenished until the entire solution had frozen across the temperature gradient. Samples were then lyophilized for 48 hours. Prior to sterilization and seeding, films and sponges were submerged in 1M sodium carbonate for 1 hour at room temperature and subsequently rinsed three times in distilled water for 20 minutes and soaked in distilled water overnight. For hydrated mechanical analysis, sectioned sponges were soaked in PBS prior to testing.

Cell Seeding – Sponges used for seeding were cylinders 6 mm in diameter and 1.5 mm thick. They were sterilized for 24 hours with 70% ethanol and UV exposure, then soaked in growth media overnight. They were then seeded with 1,000,000 DrAMPCs in 50 μ L of media and incubated for 4 hours before 1 mL of media was added to each well. Films were cast in 24-well plates and seeded at medium (75,000 DrAMPCs/cm²) or high (300,000 DrAMPCs/cm²). Media changes were performed once per week.

Mechanical Testing - Compression tests were performed on an Instron 3366 from TA Instruments (New Castle, TE) with a strain rate of 1 mm/min to a total strain of 30%, and modulus values were calculated for the 2%-10% compression interval. Samples were tested in the hydrated state (immersed in 1X PBS). Sponge dimensions used were 8x8x8 mm cubes.

Nutrition Testing - DrAMPC and C2C12 cells were cultured and harvested into aliquots of 20 million and 10 million cells respectively for nutritional analysis. Cells were lysed with RIPA buffer (ThermoFisher, #89900) and 1% Halt Protease Inhibitor Cocktail EDTA-Free (ThermoFisher, #78425). Protein was quantified by a Pierce BCA Protein Assay Kit (ThermoFisher, #23225) according to manufacturer instructions. Iron and zinc were quantified

by an Iron Assay Kit (Abcam, #ab83366) and Zinc Assay Kit (Abcam, #ab102507) according to manufacturer instructions. For iron fortification experiments, cells were cultured with 10% Iron-Fortified Bovine Serum (Sigma-Aldrich, #12138C). Microplate measurements were performed on a SpectraMax M2 reader (Molecular Devices).

Thermogravimetric Analysis - Thermogravimetric analysis with ramped heat was performed on samples of chitosan sponge with a Thermogravimetric Analyzer (TA Instruments, #Q500). Samples were heated from room temperature to 500°C at a rate of 20°C per minute.

Statistical Analysis – Statistical analysis was performed with GraphPad Prism 7.04 software. Error bars in column charts are standard deviations. Statistical significance was determined via two-way ANOVA and multiple comparisons with the Sidak post-hoc test or via multiple *t* tests with the Holm-Sidak post-hoc test with alpha = 0.05. Additional info as well as the p-values for each statistically significant comparison are listed in Table SI3.

Results

Adaptation of insect muscle cells to serum-free media and inducing single-cell suspension culture

A primary goal of our research was to adapt insect muscle cells to serum-free media. We adapted the cells either immediately from 0% to 100% EC405 (Fig. 1, b), or gradually over the course of two weeks by passaging the cells in increasing concentrations of EC405 (Fig. 1, c). A subset of cells was maintained in serum-supplemented media as a control (Fig. 1, a). Details of the adaptation schedule are listed in Table SI1. The immediately adapted cells initially

proliferated at rates equivalent to the control cells, however, after the first 48 hours the growth rate decreased. After one week in culture, the growth of immediately adapted cells was stagnant and the cell morphology appeared more neuron-like than myoblast-like; with multiple cell extensions protruding from the cell body (Fig. 1, b). The gradually adapted cells retained their myoblast-like morphology identified by slight elongation (Fig. 1, c) and exhibited comparable growth rates to controls (Fig. 1, d). As shown in Fig. 1, d, the insect muscle cells appear to exhibit diauxic growth. The two growth phases are distinguished by adherent growth and suspension growth. At low to medium cell densities, the cells are adherent. They proliferate until the surface is over-confluent (growth phase 1) and subsequently begin growing in suspension (growth phase 2).

Figure 1. Insect muscle cell adaptation to serum-free media and transition from monolayer to single-cell suspension culture. (a) Fluorescence microscopy image of DrAMPCs cultured with control media for 5 days. (b) Fluorescence microscopy image of DrAMPCs cultured for 5 days after being transferred from control media to EC405 media. (c) Fluorescence microscopy image of DrAMPCs cultured for 5 days after being adapted from control media to EC405 media. (d) Growth curve of DrAMPCs cultured in control media or EC405 after gradual adaptation. The cell population was quantified from Fiji image analysis and is displayed relative to the cell population as measured on Day 1. Error bars are standard

deviations (n=5), and replicates are separate 24-wells. (e) Phase contrast image of DrAMPCs cultured on a plasma-treated culture surface. (f) Phase contrast image of DrAMPCs cultured on an ultra-low attachment culture surface. (g) Fluorescence microscopy image of DrAMPCs after 1 week in agitated suspension culture in EC405 media. (h) Fluorescence microscopy image of DrAMPCs after 1 week in agitated suspension culture in EC405 media supplemented with 100 µg/mL dextran sulfate.

Once the DrAMPC culture exhibited steady growth in EC405, the monolayer culture was transitioned to suspension culture. It was noted that when static culture flasks became over-confluent, the cells continued to grow in three-dimensional aggregates or in suspension. When the plasma-treated culture surface (Fig. 1, e) was switched with an ultra-low attachment surface (Fig. 1, f), the DrAMPCs did not attach and instead proliferated in suspension, at first as single cells and then forming aggregates, reaching a maximum cell density of 1E6 cells/mL after 5 days. The cells were then transitioned from static suspension culture to agitated suspension culture with the use of shaker flasks incubated at room temperature. In agitated suspension, the cells formed aggregates (Fig. 1, g). However, the addition of 100 µg/mL dextran sulfate was sufficient to reduce aggregation and promote a single cell suspension (Fig. 1, h). After expansion in suspension culture and removal of dextran sulfate, the cells transitioned back to adherent monolayers and retained a myoblast-like morphology.

Comparison of mammalian vs. insect muscle cell survival and growth in starvation conditions

DrAMPC cells were noted to be capable of long-term survival and growth without media refreshment. To investigate this, DrAMPCs and C2C12 mouse myoblast cells were cultured in

parallel to compare the survival of mammalian vs. insect muscle cells in limited nutrient conditions. Cells were initially fed 5 mL of media per well in a 6-well plate and subsequently left undisturbed until time point analysis. The C2C12 cells decreased in cell viability and total cell number over the course of 25 days in culture (Fig. 2, a & b). By day 25, the majority of cells had detached from the culture surface and were <20% viable. The DrAMPCs continued to proliferate up to day 20, after which most of the cells also detached from the cell surface. However, unlike the C2C12s, the detached DrAMPCs remained viable, with 70% viability observed after 25 days (Fig. 2, b & c). Only a small fraction of nonviable cells was observed in the center of large cell aggregates. In separate experiments, DrAMPCs were observed to survive for over two months without media refreshment. Viability only declined past 50% when components of the media began to crystalize as a result of water evaporation (Fig. S14).

Figure 2. Comparison of insect and mammalian muscle cell survival and growth during long-term absence of media refreshment. (a) Change in C2C12 and DrAMPC populations relative to the populations determined at Day 5. Populations were quantified from Fiji image analysis. Error bars are standard deviations (n=6); replicates are separate images. (b) Cell

viability of C2C12 and DrAMPC populations as quantified from Fiji analysis of Live/Dead stained images. Error bars are standard deviations (n=6); replicates are separate images. Statistical significance was determined via the Holm-Sidak method, with alpha=0.05. (c) Fluorescence microscopy images of Live/Dead stained C2C12 and DrAMPC populations over time. White arrows on Day 25 indicate the cellular aggregates detached from the culture surface.

Effect of insect hormones on insect muscle cell proliferation and differentiation

DrAMPCs were treated with methoprene (JH), a juvenile hormone mimic and insecticide, to investigate the effect of the hormone on cell proliferation. Cells treated with JH exhibited higher proliferation than control groups at both day 1 and 5 time points although the 500 ng/mL treatment level had a larger effect than the 1,000 ng/mL treatment (Fig. 3, a). Aside from increasing cell numbers, JH treatment inhibited cell elongation, a preliminary sign of differentiation. The average length of JH-treated (500 ng/mL) cells was 8 μm less than the control cells (Fig. 3, b & d).

Figure 3. Effect of insect juvenile and molting hormones on *in vitro* proliferation and differentiation of insect muscle cells. (a) Cell population after treatment with 0, 500 or 1000 ng/mL of methoprene as measured via a CyQuant proliferation assay. Error bars are standard deviations (n=5); replicates are separate 96-wells. Statistical significance was determined via

the Holm-Sidak method, with $\alpha=0.05$. (b) Histogram of cell lengths of cultures treated with 0 or 500 ng/mL JH as measured via Fiji image analysis. (c) Cell population after treatment with 0, 500 or 1000 ng/mL of 20-HE as measured via a CyQuant proliferation assay. Error bars are standard deviations ($n=5$). Differences between averages were not statistically significant. (d) Fluorescence microscopy images of DrAMPCs treated with 0 or 500 ng/mL JH after 4 days in culture. Red circles indicate elongated cells. (e) Fluorescence microscopy images of DrAMPCs treated with 40 ng/mL 20-HE.

Cells were also treated with insect molting hormone, 20-hydroxyecdysone (20-HE). Growth rates of 20-HE treated cells did not significantly differ from control groups (Fig. 3, c).

Concentrations as low as 40 ng/mL 20-HE were able to trigger cell elongation, a preliminary sign of differentiation (Fig. 3, e). When cells were treated with both JH and 20-HE, cell proliferation increased slightly but not significantly. It was noted that the cell population was consistently heterogeneous, with a fraction of cells elongating and fusing while the majority of cells remain spherical. To probe for differences in the cell population, we stained the cells for ecdysone receptor (EcdR), the receptor responsible for binding 20-HE to trigger molting *in vivo* or differentiation *in vitro*. All cells expressed EcdR, regardless of whether or not they initiated differentiation (Fig. 4, a).

Figure 4. Confirmation of muscle identity and cellular contractions induced by extracellular potassium. (a) Confocal microscopy image of DrAMPCs immunostained for ecdysone receptor and DAPI. (b) Fluorescence microscopy image of DrAMPCs immunostained for myosin heavy chain and DAPI after 5 days of differentiation with 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ 20-HE in EC405. (c) Phase contrast image of DrAMPCs immediately before and after treatment with media supplemented with 600 mM K^+ . Red circles indicate myoblasts contracting upon K^+ treatment.

Induced insect muscle cell contraction by external potassium

The study that generated the DrAMPC line previously demonstrated that the cells cultured in serum-supplemented media undergo differentiation upon treatment with 20-HE. A small fraction of our EC405 adapted cells were also triggered by 20-HE to differentiate and form long, multinucleated myotubes that express myosin heavy chain; a skeletal muscle biomarker (Fig. 4, b). Spontaneous cell contractions were not observed during our experiments, although they have been noted in previous research¹⁰. To demonstrate the contractile capacity of DrAMPCs, the cultures were treated with high concentrations of extracellular potassium (Fig. 4, b). Intracellular potassium concentrations in Diptera muscle range between 142 and 179 mM²⁵. The cells did not contract when treated with 300 mM K⁺ but did contract when treated with 600 mM K⁺. The cells were 95% viable after potassium treatment. Cell fractional shortening was determined by images analysis. On average, the myoblasts (elongated cells) contracted by 31.6% ± 14.8% (n=12). In contrast, the spherical, proliferative precursor cells shortened by 1.6% ± 16.2% (n=14).

Insect muscle cell growth on chitosan-based scaffolds

Flat films were fabricated from mushroom-based chitosan and seeded with DrAMPCs (Fig. 5, a). After 24 hours and at medium seeding densities, DrAMPCs favored adhesion to low concentration films (1%, 2%), however, after multiple days in culture all films became confluent. At high seeding densities, cells attach to all films (Fig. 5 b) after 24 hours. Cellular adhesion was assessed on tissue culture plastic controls and chitosan films. On day 1 in culture, the total cell population was compared to the adherent cell population by assaying wells as they were (Total) or after being aspirated and rinsed with PBS (Adherent) (Fig. 5 c). The total cell population on tissue culture plastic was greater than the total cell population on

the chitosan films, however, the differences in adherent cell populations between conditions were not statistically significant. This indicates that cells may grow more quickly on tissue culture plastic and the difference between total and adherent cells on the plastic may be due to cell growth in suspension after reaching confluence on the surface. To investigate the effect of a surface coating on cell adhesion, a subset of films was coated with 0.1% gelatin solution. Gelatin did improve cell adhesion to tissue culture plastic (Fig. 5, d). On gelatin-coated films, cells appeared to grow in aggregates and were detached from the center of the well during the PBS rinse (Fig. S11). Because the detrimental effect was not observed in the control, it may be due to interactions (or lack thereof) between the chitosan surface and gelatin coating. At day 1, there were no significant differences between cell adhesion to tissue culture plastic and the three film concentrations (Fig. 5, e). By day 5, the tissue culture plastic conditions contained roughly twice the amount of adherent viable cells as day 1. Cells grew on the chitosan films to a lesser extent but more importantly remained adherent and viable.

Figure 5. Adhesion and growth of insect muscle cells mushroom chitosan films. (a) SEM images of the middle and edge morphology of a 2% chitosan film. Films of other concentrations were similar in appearance. (b) Fluorescence microscopy images of DrAMPCs at medium (75,000 cells/cm²) and high (300,000 cells/cm²) seeding densities on chitosan films of variable concentrations after 24 hours in culture. (c) Viable cells on chitosan films or control conditions quantified via MTS assay. Films and controls were assayed after 24 hours in culture (initial seeding density of 300,000 cells/cm²) as they were (Total) or after being aspirated and rinsed with PBS (Adherent). (d) Percentage of adherent, viable cells determined via MTS assay on untreated or 0.1% gelatin coated films or controls. (e) Viable, adherent cells determined via MTS assay quantified after 24 hours and on day 5 of culture.

To translate the culture to 3D, chitosan sponges with aligned microtubular pores were fabricated using a directional freezing technique (Fig. 6, a). DrAMPCs were cultured in chitosan sponges for one week (Fig. 6, b) or two weeks (Fig. SI3). At both time points, cells showed adhesion on all sponges (1, 2, 4% chitosan) and formed a nearly confluent monolayer. When treated with 20-hydroxyecdysone, a small fraction (<1%) of cells on the chitosan scaffolds differentiated (Fig. 6, c). The average myocyte length on tissue culture plastic is 82 $\mu\text{m} \pm 40 \mu\text{m}$ (n=19) and the average myocyte length on chitosan is 68 $\pm 34 \mu\text{m}$ (n=7). The lengths are not statistically significant via unpaired t-test with a p-value of 0.5568. The longest myocyte observed on plastic was 143 μm while the longest myocyte observed on chitosan was 120 μm . Myocyte lengths between chitosan scaffolds did not differ significantly. In select areas of growth, cells appeared to be in alignment with the length of the microtubular pores (Fig. 6, d). Although cells grown on the 1% sponges exhibited strong adhesion, the sponges were extremely fragile and did not retain an aligned pore morphology when sectioned. After two

weeks in culture, the 1% sponges disintegrated into sheet-like pieces while the 2% and 4% sponges were more durable. The mechanical properties of the sponges can be tuned via chitosan concentration²⁶. Elastic modulus values of the 2% and 4% sponges were determined via hydrated compression testing (Fig. 6, e). The stiffness of both sponges in the cross-section direction was approximately 2 kPa. The moduli differed in the lateral direction, the 4% sponge being approximately twice as stiff as the 2% sponge. The mushroom-derived sponges in this study were less stiff than the comparable chitosan-derived sponges tested in Jana et al., 2013 (5 kPa versus 21 kPa for 4% sponges), a discrepancy which may be due to differences in initial molecular weight of the polymers²⁶. Both works show a similar trend of significant differences in moduli measured in the lateral direction rather than the cross-section direction of compression.

Figure 6. Adhesion and differentiation of insect muscle cells on chitosan sponge scaffolds. (a) SEM images of cross-section and lateral views of a 2% chitosan sponge. Sponges of other concentrations were similar in appearance. (b) Confocal images of DrAMPCs on chitosan sponges of variable concentrations after 1 week in culture in control media. (c) Fluorescence microscopy images of chitosan sponges with and without hormone treatment. (d) Fluorescence microscopy image of DrAMPCs on a 4% chitosan sponge after 10 days of growth in EC405 media. The white arrow indicates the orientation of the aligned microtubular pore. (e) Elastic moduli of chitosan sponges obtained via hydrated compression tests performed in either the cross-sectional or lateral direction (error bars are standard deviations, n=5). The schematic demonstrates the direction of compression.

Preliminary data on the thermal degradation of chitosan was collected to provide initial insight into how chitosan sponges degrade under simulated cooking. Thermogravimetric analysis with ramped heat was performed from room temperature to 500°C with a rate of 20°C per minute. Chitosan powder begins to degrade at 325°C and degradation is not significantly affected by heating rate (Fig. SI2). There are three phases of degradation: (1) volatilization of residual materials, (2) chitosan chain degradation and (3) decomposition of remaining carbon²⁷.

Nutritional properties of insect vs. mammalian muscle cell cultures

In order to probe nutrition differences between mammalian and insect muscle cells, we measured cellular protein and select mineral content of DrAMPC and C2C12 cells. Both cell cultures were assayed for total protein, iron and zinc (Table 1). Per cell, the C2C12 cells

contain more (by factors of 2.5, 2.9 and 3.4, respectively) protein, iron and zinc than DrAMPC cells. However, the C2C12 cells (average diameter = 19.60 μm) are much larger than DrAMPCs (average diameter = 5.72 μm). Correcting for cell size, DrAMPCs contain a higher density of all three compounds per unit volume. These results correlate with *in vivo* nutrient values for the corresponding whole organisms as fruit fly tissue contains equivalent protein and a higher density of iron and zinc compared to mouse tissue (Table SI4). This provides preliminary evidence that as insects are often more nutrient rich compared to mammalian tissue, insect cells may also be more nutritious than mammalian cells.

Table 1. Protein and mineral content, cell dimensions of immortalized mouse and fly muscle cell lines.

Cell Line	Protein (pg/cell)	Iron (pg/cell)	Zinc (pg/cell)	Suspended Cell Diameter (μm)
C2C12	1393 \pm 119	35.39 \pm 0.34	156.14 \pm 3.08	19.60 \pm 1.95
DrAMPC	558 \pm 67	12.09 \pm 0.40	46.02 \pm 2.16	5.72 \pm 0.81

In a simple attempt to increase iron content, we cultured DrAMPCs in media supplemented with iron-fortified serum (136 μM Fe) and compared the cellular iron content to DrAMPCs cultured with media supplemented with conventional serum (24 μM Fe). The iron-fortified DrAMPCs contained twice the concentration of iron compared to the control, although the fortified media contained roughly 6-fold the amount of iron as the control media (Table 2). This indicates that while media can be formulated to influence nutritional content, there is a limit to the amount of minerals the cells can uptake.

Table 2. Iron content of bovine serum and insect muscle cells cultured in media supplemented with 10% serum for five days.

	Iron Content of Serum (μM)	Iron Content of DrAMPCs Cultured in 10% Serum (μM)
Fetal Bovine Serum	24.35 \pm 0.58	27.06 \pm 0.90
Iron-Fortified Serum	135.65 \pm 5.51	62.40 \pm 1.25

Discussion

Key challenges in the field of cultured muscle biomass for non-medical applications can be addressed with invertebrate cell sources. The main challenges include producing cells in a cost-efficient manner and transforming the cell mass into functional constructs. The majority of cell lines that have been scaled for industrial production are derived from humans (e.g., HEK 293, HeLa S3, WI-38), rodents (e.g., CHO-K1, NS0, BEK) and insects (e.g., S2, Sf9, High Five)²⁸. In most cases these cells are not the end-product themselves, but rather are utilized to produce valuable therapeutic proteins (e.g., antibodies, cytokines, growth factors). The most commonly utilized cell lines share characteristics in that they are immortalized and can achieve high growth densities in serum-free, suspension culture.

So far, muscle cells have only been produced in relatively small quantities for research. A key step towards industrial-scale muscle cell culture is formulation of, and adaptation to, serum-free media. Serum is expensive and susceptible to batch-to-batch variability and cost fluctuations based on supply availability²⁹. For cultured meat applications, serum must be eliminated from culture media to reduce costs and allow for animal-free production. Serum-free

media formulations have been reported for mammalian muscle cells, however, they are supplemented with animal-derived or recombinant proteins (e.g., fetuin, fibroblast growth factor, insulin)³⁰⁻³³ and to our knowledge, not commercially available. In this work, a *D. melanogaster* muscle progenitor cell line was successfully adapted to Ex-Cell 405 serum-free insect media. Although this particular medium is proprietary, other insect cells have been adapted from Ex-Cell 405 media to defined, low-cost formulations with IPL-41 basal media (the preparation is publicly available)^{23,34}. Future work could include optimizing in-house media formulations.

The extended survival and proliferation of insect muscle cells in the absence of fresh media is demonstrated in this work and by previous studies from our lab¹⁴. We previously observed that primary cultures of *M. sexta* cells survived over 75 days in the same media and theorized the effect may be due to supporting yolk and fat cell types which store nutrients. The present work utilized an immortalized cell line and we observed cell survival without nutrient exchange for more than two months. We propose that the extended survival may be attributed to differences in mammalian versus insect metabolism. In a study comparing mammalian and insect glucose and glutamine metabolism, insect cells uniquely channeled glucose metabolites into the tricarboxylic acid cycle which produced more energy per unit glucose than glycolysis³⁵. Insect cells also do not produce significant lactate, the accumulation of which significantly lowers the pH of mammalian muscle cell cultures.

Mammalian muscle cells generally grow as adherent rather than suspension cultures. Cost-efficient production would require suspension cultures of stem cells with myogenic-lineage, adaptation of muscle progenitor cells to suspension cultures or

development of more complex bioreactor systems suitable for adherent cell types (e.g., microcarriers, hollow fibers). The results from the present study demonstrated that the DrAMPC line of invertebrate muscle cells can be grown in single-cell suspension cultures and transition back to monolayer cultures after expansion. Dextran sulfate supplementation was sufficient to reduce cell aggregation, and shaker flask agitation kept cells in suspension. Removal of dextran sulfate and reduction of cell density in static cultures promoted monolayer culture and cell elongation. This versatility and adaptability allows for streamlined production and scale-up.

For industrial bioprocesses, it will be advantageous to control proliferation and differentiation of muscle cells via external factors. Methoprene and 20-hydroxyecdysone have previously been shown to affect the growth and development of insect cells *in vitro*^{36–38}. In the present study, methoprene increased proliferation and 20-hydroxyecdysone triggered differentiation in both serum-supplemented and serum-free cultures. Methoprene is used as an insecticide generated via chemical synthesis³⁹ for the production of many agricultural products. It poses minimal risk to the environment, and guidelines for human consumption have been developed (recommended exposure is set at 0.3750 mg/day for the average adult)⁴⁰. The hormone 20-hydroxyecdysone is produced by plants as well as insects and has been produced in plant *in vitro* cultures⁴¹. It is also safe for human consumption and even promoted as a fitness supplement⁴².

When applying this technology for food purposes, it is important to consider potential hazards to human health. Human health risks could arise from the original insect species, the derived cell cultures or the circulated media. Although many insect species are edible and nutritious,

some species present risks in the form of anti-nutrient substances, allergens, synthesized defense toxins, pesticides and microbial pathogens. These risks can generally be avoided by selecting safe species, decontamination and raising the insects on nontoxic feed⁴³. *D. melanogaster* flies are safe to eat and sold by companies to eat as whole larvae, oils, or powder. Because *D. melanogaster* are safe to consume, we assume cells cultured from fruit flies would be safe to consume as well, given that the cultures are fed with food-grade growth media. Human pathogens have not been detected in insect cell cultures, however, some cell lines can perform posttranslational modifications to proteins that may trigger human allergies¹¹. Due to ExCell 405 being a proprietary media formulation, we are unsure whether it contains any components that could be dangerous for consumption. However, in-house serum-free insect media formulations typically contain basal media, soy protein extract, yeast extract and lipids that are not toxic to humans²³. Cultured insect cells may be safer than whole insects as the restricted number of cell types and controlled environment may eliminate the presence of certain allergens and toxins. While primary cell lines are likely safe, concerns may rise for continuous or immortalized cell lines. Spontaneously immortalized cell lines may develop mutations overtime, and it is unclear whether this may pose a safety risk. Genetically immortalized cells may present additional concerns. The *D. melanogaster* adult muscle precursor-like cell line used in this study was immortalized via the oncogenic protein RasV12 and expresses GFP. Ingestion of GFP is unlikely to be detrimental to human health⁷. Farmed meat likely contains cancerous tissue at times and this is probably not a health risk as (1) cancer is not contagious and (2) proper cooking and digestion processes should breakdown cancerous cells. Similarly, dead cultured cells or tissues should not pose a risk for human consumption. Regardless, it is important for further research to take place surrounding the ingestion of cultured and genetically modified cell-based foods.

Large, aligned muscle tissues are necessary to produce bioactuators with useful contractile force and structured meat-like tissues for food. The construction of three-dimensional and functional mammalian muscle tissues has been widely pursued⁴⁴⁻⁴⁸. Insect muscle constructs are remarkably less researched and consist mainly of muscle explants or primary cultures self-assembled in PDMS molds^{12,49}. We evaluated mushroom-derived chitosan as a scaffolding biomaterial to support in vitro culture of insect muscle cells. Chitosan was selected as the biomaterial of choice for this system as it is (1) a well-researched biomaterial in the field of tissue engineering, (2) edible, (3) inexpensive, (4) can be acquired from animal-free sources (fungi, microbes), (5) is approved for human consumption, (6) may supply health benefits and (7) scaffold techniques for three-dimensional muscle culture have been established²⁶. In a feasible production scenario, insect cells would first be expanded in a single cell suspension culture and subsequently seeded on a static scaffold for tissue maturation. Therefore, adhesion, viability and differentiation on cell-scaffold constructs are more important factors than growth. Although gelatin coating did not increase cell adhesion to chitosan films, a different outcome may result from creating a chitosan-gelatin composite solution before casting the film as opposed to a gelatin coating. Other materials to investigate include collagen and laminin, although it is important to remember the design requirement of minimizing animal-derived byproducts. Because cells can form a confluent layer on non-functionalized chitosan films and sponges, a coating material may be unnecessary.

The purpose of modulating scaffold stiffness is to have some control over the texture and palatability of the end-product. One long-term goal of the research area is to have three-dimensional cell-scaffold constructs with mechanical properties similar to meat. The

elastic modulus of bovine muscle (mixed fiber orientation) is ~1.5 kPa. Chitosan sponges can be fabricated to have a similar stiffness, implying a chitosan-based cultured meat product could have similar texture to familiar meat products. It will also be important to investigate the mechanical properties of seeded scaffolds and the effect of cooking temperature and time.

The most prevalent challenge in this study was promoting homogenous differentiation, as the majority of cells retained a spherical morphology indicative of their proliferative state. However, on plastic and chitosan scaffolds, myosin heavy chain-expressing cells could be generated (albeit at low efficiency) after treatment with 20-hydroxyecdysone. In all control samples (plastic and sponges not treated with 20-hydroxyecdysone), no myosin heavy chain-expressing cells were observed. This supports the conclusion that while DrAMPCs have the capacity to differentiate to a muscle phenotype on plastic and 2D and 3D chitosan scaffolds, the system is lacking an element or elements necessary for robust differentiation. There is evidence from previous studies that insect muscle cells may require supporting cell types, specifically neurons, in order to fully differentiate into mature myotubes^{14,50}. Our future work will focus on achieving a greater percentage of differentiated cells by implementing co-culture and electrical stimulus methods.

Conclusions

This work lays the foundation for insect muscle tissue engineering as a tool for cultured meat production and bioactuation. While previous research has demonstrated insect cell types purposed for protein production can be adapted to serum-free medium and cultured in suspension, it was previously unclear whether the same benefits applied to insect muscle

cells. There was also a gap in scaffold design for insect-based constructs, as scaffolds have primarily been composed of PDMS which is inapplicable to food-related technologies with these *in vitro* tissues. Furthermore, while edible insects are lauded for their nutrient density, it was unknown whether *in vitro* insect cells have a desirable nutrition profile. To address these issues, we used genetically immortalized and highly proliferative *D. melanogaster* adult muscle progenitor-like cells to explore the feasibility of scalable cell production, the integration of scaffold techniques and the evaluation of nutritional content. We successfully adapted our cells to an inexpensive, serum-free media formulation and transitioned the cells from adherent to suspension cultures. We also compared the long-term survival of DrAMPCs in limited nutrient conditions to survival of the mouse-derived myoblast C2C12 cell line to highlight the benefits of the insect cells. To develop scaffolds inspired by insect cuticle, we fabricated films and sponges from mushroom-derived chitosan to develop 2D and 3D culture systems. Lastly, we analyzed the protein, iron and zinc content of the DrAMPC cells compared to C2C12 cells to show the nutritional value of these *in vitro* insect cell cultures.

Description of the Supporting Information Material

The supporting information includes details about the adaptation of the cell line to serum-free media, antibody information and detailed description of statistical analysis methods. Additional figures include microscopy images from gelatin coating experiments, DrAMPC growth on chitosan sponges at 2 weeks in culture and DrAMPCs in long-term starvation culture as well as data from thermogravimetric analysis of chitosan.

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Table of Contents Graphic

Title: In Vitro Insect Muscle for Tissue Engineering Applications

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